

Synthesis and characterisation of 8-aminoquinoline complexes of platinum(II) and palladium(II). Kinetics of dimethyl sulphoxide entry into the coordination sphere

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The synthesis and characterisation of 8-aminoquinoline (8-AMQ) complexes of platinum(II) and palladium(II) have been reported. Kinetic study of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) entry into the coordination sphere of $\text{Pt}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Pd}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ has been undertaken through spectrophotometric measurements showing the replacement of one Cl^- from the complexes. ^1H nmr studies support the S-bonding to the metal centre in the DMSO substituted species.

Extensive studies have been carried out on the unique chemotherapeutic properties of the drug *cis*-diamminodichloroplatinum(II) (cisplatin) in the last 25 years or so¹⁻³. A number of studies have also investigated on the relative merits of numerous analogs of cisplatin. In the course of our research on the reactivity of several nucleophiles towards platinum(II) and palladium(II) complexes, we noted that 8-aminoquinoline (=8-AMQ), a typically asymmetric bidentate chelating ligand, is capable of binding to platinum(II) and palladium(II) through the two different types of nitrogen donor atoms. The present work thus describes the synthesis and characterisation of the Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of 8-AMQ. The kinetics of dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) entry into the coordination moiety of the $\text{Pt}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Pd}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ complexes measured through uv-vis spectroscopy and substantiated by ^1H nmr measurements is also narrated. To the best of our knowledge, no such study has been reported earlier.

Results and Discussion

Both the $\text{Pt}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Pd}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ complexes are soluble in dimethylformamide resulting in blue and pink solutions respectively. In each case the colour change takes place on addition of dimethyl sulphoxide, the blue solution of $\text{Pt}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ slowly turns pink-violet and the pink solution of $\text{Pd}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2$ to red at a faster rate. There are significant differences among the uv-visible spectra recorded in solid state and in dimethylformamide (DMF) medium of these complexes. This supports the interaction among the solvent and the complexes. Probably two DMF molecules interact axially (along the z-axis) with the square-planar moiety of the complex. This type of interaction is also observed in acetonitrile and butyronitrile solutions leading to spectral changes. The possibility of DMF entry through chloride ion replacement is excluded since the equivalent conductance of the complex solutions in DMF medium remains within 0-5 mho and does not

Fig. 1. ^1H nmr signal changes with time for the aromatic protons of $[\text{Pt}(8\text{-AMQ})\text{Cl}_2]$ in DMSO-d_6 solvent (a) after 35 min, (b) after 3 h and (c) after 7 h of mixing

change with time. Both Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂ and Pd(8-AMQ)Cl₂ complexes show ν_{N-H} asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations recorded at 3120, 3040 and 3320, 2900 cm⁻¹

Fig. 2. Spectral scan for the reaction of Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂ with DMSO in DMF medium; temp = 40°, [complex] = 1.3 × 10⁻⁵ and [DMSO] = 11.75 M

respectively. For the free ligand (i.e. 8-AMQ) these are at 3450 and 3349 cm⁻¹ respectively. The stretching vibrations are reduced by ~200–300 cm⁻¹ upon coordination to platinum(II) and palladium(II) centre which is quite expected⁴. Both the complexes show ν_{M-Cl} stretching bands near ~340–330 cm⁻¹ (M = Pt, Pd). From ¹H nmr spectra of these complexes (in DMSO-d₆) only H⁷ of 8-AMQ moiety can be assigned properly. Multiplets appear at ~7.3–8.0 and ~8.7–9.0 ppm due to complicated coupling of aromatic protons and peak shift caused by DMSO entry which are likely to occur. The ¹H nmr signals for the aromatic protons in [Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂] change with time (Fig. 1) suggesting the Pt-S bond formation. Due to the Pt-S bond formation, the pi-electron cloud of sulphur-oxygen

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the reaction of [Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂] and DMSO in dimethyl formamide medium

Temp = 40°, I = 0.0, [complex] = 1 × 10⁻⁵ M

[DMSO] M	10 ⁴ k _{obs} s ⁻¹
1.17	3.53
4.70	4.79
9.40	6.65
11.75	7.53

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the reaction of [Pd(8-AMQ)Cl₂] and DMSO in dimethyl formamide medium

Temp. = 40°, I = 0.0, [complex] = 1 × 10⁻⁵ M

[DMSO] M	10 ³ k _{obs} s ⁻¹
1.17	1.92
4.70	2.30
9.40	2.76
11.75	3.12

multiple bond in DMSO approaches closely to the 8-AMQ moiety. Hence the aromatic protons interact with the pi-electron cloud of sulphur-oxygen bond causing significant changes in ¹H nmr signals. The presence of more than one isosbestic points in the spectral scan (Fig. 2) strongly suggests that the original reactant is being replaced by one product, or if by more than one product, that these are always in a strictly constant ratio⁵. Conductometric measurement of the product solutions shows an equivalent conductance value (35–40 mho) which is less than that of 1 : 1 electrolyte in the medium, and the following equilibrium may be of significance :

Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}, s⁻¹) for the reaction of [Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂] with DMSO are listed in Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the reaction of [Pd(8-AMQ)Cl₂] with DMSO are listed in Table 2. The least-squares plots of k_{obs} vs [DMSO] for these reactions suggest that the rate law would involve a small contribution of DMSO-independent path (k₀) along with the first order, dependent substitution (k₁) by DMSO according to

$$k_{obs} = k_0 + k_1 [DMSO] \quad (1)$$

The evaluated parameters are listed in Table 3. The k₀ path reflects the back-reaction as evidenced from conductometric results, and can be distinguished from the usual solvolytic path encountered in square-planar substitution. It may be noted that the Pd^{II} complex reacts almost three times faster than the Pt^{II} analog in tune with the general trend of reactivity in d⁸ systems. In both cases, however, the reaction proceeds through associative mechanism via the formation of an unstable five-coordinated trigonal bipyramidal intermediate. For [Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂] this can be depicted as follows :

Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} being soft bases prefer soft sulfur atom rather than oxygen atom of DMSO for binding. In 8-AMQ, two N-donor sites are not equivalent—one is quinoline nitrogen atom and the other amino nitrogen atom. Owing to the more *s*-character of the quinoline nitrogen atom, it will exert greater *trans*-effect than the amino nitrogen atom. Probably DMSO entry will take place at the *trans*-position of the quinoline nitrogen atom. Product of these reactions are [Pt(8-AMQ)(DMSO)Cl]Cl and [Pd(8-AMQ)(DMSO)Cl]Cl which are present in equilibria as denoted earlier. These products are stable only in solution but prolonged keeping could result in isomerisation to the *cis*-analog as noted from the slight shifting of the isobestic point (~600 nm) in the scan spectra of the Pt^{II} system. This type of isomerisation is well-documented in DMSO complexes of Pt^{II} ^{6,7}. Unfortunately we could not isolate the DMSO substituted products by keeping the reaction solution for 2–3 months or by evaporation of the solvent at high temperature. In either case, Pt-black or Pd-black is formed showing instability of these complexes.

Table 3. Second order rate constants (k_1) and the back-reaction paths (k_0) in the reaction of [Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂] and [Pd(8-AMQ)Cl₂] with DMSO in dimethyl formamide (The other conditions are same)

Complex	$10^4 k_1$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^3 k_0$ s ⁻¹
[Pt(8-AMQ)Cl ₂]	0.38 ± 0.01	0.30 ± 0.01
[Pd(8-AMQ)Cl ₂]	1.11 ± 0.06	1.78 ± 0.05

Experimental

Potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II), K₂PtCl₄, palladium chloride, PdCl₂ (both Arora-Matthey Limited, India) and 8-aminoquinoline (Aldrich) were used for synthesis. Solvents used for spectroscopic and synthetic works were spectroscopically pure dimethyl sulphoxide and dimethylformamide (SRL, India). These solvents were further purified by distillation before use.

Kinetic study and spectral scans were carried out using a Shimadzu UV 2100 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Bruker avance DPX 300 machine (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. Elemental analyses were performed in a 2400 Series-II CHN Perkin-Elmer analyzer.

(8-Aminoquinoline)dichloroplatinum(II) : To potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II), K₂PtCl₄ (0.104 g, 0.25 mmol) dissolved in water (10 ml), 8-aminoquinoline (0.036 g, 0.25 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The stirring was continued at 40° for ~0.5 h. A brown precipitate separated gradually. The product was filtered, washed several times with water and dry ethanol to remove all unreacted starting materials and vacuum-dried (~80%) (Found : C, 26.49; H, 2.00; N, 6.31. C₉N₂H₈Cl₂Pt calcd. for : C, 26.34; H, 1.95; N 6.28%); λ_{max} (nujol) 367, 206.5 nm; λ_{max} (dimethylformamide) 569 (16600), 366.5 (46400),

283.5 nm (ε = 128400 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹).

(8-Aminoquinoline)dichloropalladium(II) : To potassium tetrachloropalladate(II), K₂PdCl₄ (0.326 g, 1.0 mmol) dissolved in water (10 ml), 8-aminoquinoline (0.144 g, 0.25 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred at 40° for ~0.5 h. A pale brown precipitate separated gradually. The product was filtered, washed several times with water and dry ethanol to remove all unreacted starting materials and vacuum-dried (~75%) (Found : C, 33.51; H, 2.46; N, 8.59, C₉N₂H₈Cl₂Pd calcd. for : C, 33.59; H, 2.49; N, 8.70%); λ_{max} (nujol) 482, 411.5, 331.5 nm; λ_{max} (dimethylformamide) 576 (14400), 373 (23300), 276.50 nm (ε = 137300 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹).

Kinetics : The reactions of 8-AMQ complexes with dimethyl sulphoxide were initiated by adding an accurate volume of a concentrated freshly prepared solution of the Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂ and Pd(8-AMQ)Cl₂ (such that its final concentration attained 1 × 10⁻⁵ M) in pure DMF to a DMF solution of DMSO, i.e. the nucleophile under study, previously brought to the reaction temperature (40°) in the thermostated cell of the spectrophotometer. The density of the DMSO used was previously determined through specific gravity measurement; hence, the respective concentrations may be calculated from this. To maintain the pseudo-first order conditions, concentration of DMSO was always kept large enough. All the reactions were studied at an ionic strength *I* = 0.0 as both the complexes are neutral. After preliminary repetitive scanning in the range 250–700 nm, the kinetics of DMSO entry were carried out following the increase in absorbance as a function of time at fixed wavelengths 279 and 275 nm for the Pt(8-AMQ)Cl₂ and Pd(8-AMQ)Cl₂ complexes respectively. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs} , s⁻¹) were obtained from the plots of log (A₀ - A_∞)/(A_t - A_∞) vs time or from a nonlinear least-square fit of experimental data to A_t = A_∞ + (A₀ - A_∞)e^{-kt} [A₀ = absorbance after mixing of reactants; A_∞ = absorbance at completion of reaction]. Rate constants are accurate within ±5%.

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References

1. J. J. Roberts and A. J. Thompson, *Prog. Nucleic Acid Res. Mol. Biol.*, 1979, **22**, 71.
2. W. I. Sundquist and S. J. Lippard, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **100**, 293.
3. A. J. Wagstaff, A. Ward, P. Benfield and R. C. Heel, *Drugs*, 1989, **37**, 162.

4. C. Engelter, G. E. Jackson, C. L. Knight and D. A. Thornton, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1989, **20**, 289.
5. R. G. Wilkins, "Kinetics and Mechanism of Reactions of Transition Metal Complexes", 2nd. ed., VCH, Weinheim, 1991, p.156.
6. L. E. Erickson, J. W. Cartmell and N. G. Albrecht, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 135.
7. L. E. Erickson, T. A. Ferrett and L. F. Buhse, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 1461.